

1 **RNNING TITLE: HEAT STRESS, AMINO ACID SUPPLY, AND MAMMARY CELL**
2 **FUNCTION**

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4 **Enhanced supply of methionine or arginine alters mechanistic target of**
5 **rapamycin signaling proteins, messenger RNA, and microRNA abundance in**
6 **heat-stressed bovine mammary epithelial cells in vitro**

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ABSTRACT

Heat stress (HS) causes reductions in milk production, but it is unclear whether this effect is due to reduced number or functional capacity (or both) of mammary cells. Methionine supplementation improves milk protein, whereas Arg is uptaken in excess by mammary cells to produce energy and nonessential AA that can be incorporated into milk protein. To evaluate molecular mechanisms by which mammary functional capacity is affected by HS and Met or Arg, MAC-T cells were incubated at thermal-neutral (TN; 37 °C) or heat stress (HS; 42 °C) temperatures. Treatments were optimal AA profiles (control, Lys:Met = 2.9:1.0; Lys:Arg = 2.1:1.0), control plus Met (Lys:Met = 2.5:1.0), or control plus Arg (Lys:Arg = 1.0:1.0). After incubation for 6 h, cells were harvested and RNA and protein extracted for quantitative RT-PCR and Western blotting. Protein abundance of mechanistic target of rapamycin (MTOR), eukaryotic initiation factor 2a (EIF2A), serine-threonine protein kinase (AKT), 4E binding protein 1 (EIF4EBP1), and phosphorylated EIF4EBP1 (p-EIF4EBP1) was lower during HS. The lower p-EIF4EBP1 with HS would diminish translation initiation and reduce protein synthesis. Both Met and Arg had no effect on MTOR proteins, but the phosphorylated EIF4EBP1 decreased by AA, especially Arg. Additionally, Met but not Arg decreased the abundance of phosphorylated EEF2, which could be positive for protein synthesis. Although HS upregulated the heat shock protein *HSPA1A*, the apoptotic gene *BAX*, and the translation inhibitor *EIF4EBP1*, the mRNA abundance of *PPARG*, *FASN*, *ACACA* (lipogenesis) and *BCL2L1* (anti-apoptotic) decreased. Greater supply of Met or Arg reversed most of the effects of HS occurring at the mRNA level and upregulated the abundance of *HSPA1A*. In addition, compared with control, supply of Met or Arg upregulated genes related to transcription and translation (*MAPK1*, *MTOR*, *SREBF1*, *RPS6KB1*, *JAK2*), insulin signaling (*AKT2*, *IRS1*), AA transport (*SLC1A5*, *SLC7A1*),

40 and cell proliferation (*MKI67*). Upregulation of miRNA related to cell growth arrest and
41 apoptosis (34a, 92a, 99, and 184) and oxidative stress (141 and 200a) coupled with
42 downregulation of fat synthesis-related miRNA (27ab and 221) were detected with HS. Results
43 suggest that heat stress has a direct negative effect on synthesis of protein and fat, mediated in
44 part by coordinated changes in mRNA, miRNA, and protein abundance of key networks. The
45 positive responses with Met and Arg raise the possibility that supplementation with these AA
46 during heat stress might have a positive effect on mammary metabolism.

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48 **Key words:** essential amino acids, lactation, mammary function, nutrition

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INTRODUCTION

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Compared to thermal-neutral (TN) conditions, heat stress (HS) reduces milk yield and content of fat and protein in milk (Hamzaoui et al., 2013; Salama et al., 2016). Dairy animals under HS experience reduced N intake because of decreasing DMI, N losses in sweat (Joshi et al., 1968), and reduced rumen microbial protein synthesis (Hyder et al., 2017). This may cause shortages in the essential AA needed for milk protein synthesis, and consequently a reduction in milk protein. Whether the lack of essential AA during HS affects milk protein synthesis in mammary cells is not well known. High temperatures can inhibit the growth of cells and results in alterations in structural proteins, membrane permeability (increase in intracellular Na⁺, H⁺, and Ca²⁺ concentrations) and metabolism (net reduction in cellular ATP) (Collier et al., 2006; Mu et al., 2014).

Supplementation of Met significantly improves milk protein percentage and yield in dairy cows (Lean et al., 2018). Furthermore, enhancing the supply of Met to cultured bovine mammary cells consistently upregulates mRNA abundance of *CSN1S1*, *CSN1S2*, *CSN2*, *CSN3*, *LALBA*, *JAK2*, *STAT5* and *MTOR*, which reflects an increase in protein synthesis (Nan et al., 2014; Dong et al., 2018). In context of HS, enhancing Met supply in vitro reduced apoptosis/necrosis, decreased lipid peroxidation, and increased superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione peroxidase enzymatic activity, leading to an overall cytoprotective effect during hyperthermia (Mu et al., 2014; Han et al., 2015).

The mammary gland extracts branched chain AA, Arg and Lys in excess, and uses them to produce energy or to synthesize non-essential AA (Lapierre et al., 2012). Specifically, Arg is extracted in excess and transformed to urea and ornithine (O'Quinn et al., 2002). Ornithine is the precursor of proline and several non-essential AA. Furthermore, Arg by the means of nitric oxide

73 synthase is converted to nitric oxide (O'Quinn et al., 2002) that controls blood flow (Lacasse et
74 al., 1996). Reduced mammary blood flow under HS (Lough et al., 1990) could be a cause of the
75 decrease in milk components as blood flow determines the amount of nutrients arriving in the
76 mammary for milk synthesis. Recently, Wang et al. (2014; 2017) proposed an important role for
77 Arg in the transcriptional regulation of casein genes and mechanistic target of rapamycin
78 (**MTOR**)-related genes in bovine mammary epithelial cells.

79 A number of previous studies have independently evaluated the role of essential AA on
80 mRNA abundance and MTOR signaling either in MAC-T and primary bovine mammary
81 (Appuhamy et al., 2011; Nan et al., 2014; Dong et al., 2018), or in primary mammary cells
82 exposed to HS at 42 °C (Collier et al., 2006; Kapila et al., 2013). However, there is little known
83 on the response of MTOR signaling when mammary cells are simultaneously exposed to HS and
84 supplemented with AA.

85 MicroRNA (miRNA) are small noncoding RNA that regulate gene expression at the
86 posttranscriptional level. There is evidence indicating that a number of miRNA play an important
87 role in lactation initiation and milk fat and protein syntheses in dairy cows (Do et al., 2017).
88 Furthermore, external factors that affect milk yield and quality also alter miRNA expression in
89 the mammary gland. For instance, forage source in the diet (alfalfa, corn stover or rice straw)
90 were associated with different profiles of miRNA expression in the mammary gland of dairy
91 cows (Wang et al., 2016a). As indicated above, HS reduces the content of fat and protein in milk,
92 and the published data cited above indicate that miRNA may play an important role in the
93 transcriptional regulation of genes during HS. Little is known about the role of miRNA in HS-
94 mammary cells.

95 Our hypothesis was that HS would impair cellular and molecular processes in mammary cells,
96 and the supplementation with Met and Arg could alleviate the negative effects of heat stress on
97 cell functions. Thus, the specific objective of the present experiment was to use MAC-T cells (an
98 immortalized, non-secretory bovine cell line) to study the effects of supplementation with Arg
99 and Met on the expression of genes, proteins related to MTOR and miRNA expression under TN
100 and HS conditions.

101 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

102 *Cell Culture and Treatments*

103 Unless otherwise indicated, all reagents and chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich
104 (St. Louis, MO). Frozen bovine MAC-T cells were recovered and cultured in 75-cm² flasks at
105 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂. Subcultures were repeated until enough cells
106 were obtained for the experiment. The basal medium used for cell culture was Minimum
107 Essential Medium with Earle's Balanced Salts (MEM/EBSS; GE Healthcare Life Sciences,
108 Logan, UT) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum, 5 mg/L insulin, 1 mg/L hydrocortisone,
109 5 mg/L transferrin, 5 µM/L ascorbic acid, 5 mM sodium acetate, 100 U/mL penicillin, 100
110 µg/mL streptomycin, 0.25 µg/mL antimycotic, 1 mg/L progesterone, 0.05% Lactalbumin, and
111 0.05% α-lactose. When 80-90% confluency was reached, cells were collected by trypsin-cell
112 strep and seeded in wells (for each well 20,000 cells × 9.5 cm² = 190,200 cells).

113 The protocol for cell culture used is similar to that reported previously in similar studies
114 (Peterson et al., 2004; Dong et al., 2018). Cells were allowed to grow in wells until the
115 confluency was 80-90%. Then, 3 mL of lactogenic medium was added, and plates incubated
116 overnight at 37 °C. The lactogenic medium was similar to the basal medium, except that high-
117 glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (HG-DMEM, Hyclone, GE Healthcare Life

118 Sciences, PA) was used to replace MEM/EBSS, and BSA (1 g/L) and prolactin (2.5 mg/L) were
119 supplemented. Cells were washed 3 times with PBS and 3 mL of the lactogenic medium (Table
120 1) containing 3 AA treatments was added. Cultures were performed for 6 h at 37 °C (TN) or 42
121 °C (HS). The 6-h culture time was based on similar work by Collier et al. (2006) in which the
122 mRNA abundance of HSP-70 was dramatically stimulated between 1 and 2 h and appeared to
123 peak within 4 h of exposing mammary cells to 42°C. In the same study, 162 genes had altered
124 mRNA abundance by 4 h of exposure to 42°C. The AA treatments were control with an ideal AA
125 profile (Dong et al., 2018) (**Con**), Con + 10 µg/mL methionine (**Met**), or Con + 84 µg/mL
126 arginine (**Arg**). As the mammary gland uses Arg in excess (see introduction), we decided to
127 double the concentration of Arg (from 84 to 168 µg/mL) to achieve a maximum response. The
128 level of Met used was based on previous work from our laboratory dealing with MAC-T cells
129 (Dong et al., 2018) or primary neutrophils (Abdelmegeid et al., 2017) to increase the supply of
130 Met beyond the considered ideal ratio of 2.9:1 of Lys:Met. This resulted in 6 treatment
131 combinations: TN-Con, TN-Met, TN-Arg, HS-Con, HS-Met, and HS-Arg. After the 6 h of
132 incubation cells were harvested by adding 1 mL of QIAzol reagent (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) in
133 each well for 5 min, cells were then collected and stored at -80 °C until RNA extraction and
134 western blot analysis.

135 ***RNA Extraction and Quantitative Real Time PCR***

136 Total RNA from the cells was extracted using ice-cold TRIzol reagent (Invitrogen). The RNA
137 was purified to remove genomic DNA with DNase using RNeasy Mini Kit columns (Qiagen,
138 Valencia, CA). Concentrations of RNA were measured with a NanoDrop ND-1000
139 spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, Wilmington, DE). The RNA integrity was assessed using
140 Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA). The RNA integrity number

141 values ranged from 8.6 to 9.7. A portion of the total RNA was diluted to 100 ng/μL using RNase
142 free water before cDNA synthesis.

143 The cDNA was synthesized using 100 ng total RNA, 1 μL Random Primers (Roche, Basel,
144 Switzerland), and 9 μL RNase free water. The mixture was incubated at 65 °C for 5 min in an
145 Eppendorf Mastercycler Gradient (Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA). A total of 9 μL of Master
146 Mix composed of 4 μL 5× First-Strand Buffer (Fermentas, Pittsburgh, PA), 1 μL Oligo dT18, 2
147 μL 10 mM deoxynucleotide 5'-triphosphate mix (Invitrogen), 0.25 μL Reverse aid RT
148 (Fermentas), 0.125 μL RNase Inhibitor (Fermentas), and 1.625 μL RNase free water was added.
149 The reaction was performed using the following temperature program: 25 °C for 5 min, 42 °C for
150 60 min, and 70 °C for 5 min. The cDNA was then diluted 1:4 with RNase free water.

151 The quantitative real time PCR (qPCR) was performed in a MicroAmp Optical 384-well
152 reaction plate (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA) using 4 μL diluted cDNA combined with 6
153 μL of a mixture. The mixture was composed of 5 μL 1× SYBR Green Master Mix (Quanta,
154 Gaithersburg, MD), 0.4 μL each of 10 μM forward and reverse primers, and 0.2 μL RNase free
155 water. The target genes included heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 1A (*HSPA1A*), de
156 novo fatty acids synthesis enzymes (acetyl-CoA carboxylase alpha, *ACACA*; fatty acid synthase,
157 *FASN*), AA transporters (solute carrier family 7 member 1, *SLC7A1*; solute carrier family 1
158 member 5, *SLC1A5*), milk protein gene transcription (signal transducer and activator of
159 transcription 5B, *STAT5B*; Janus kinase 2, *JAK2*), lipogenic gene transcription (sterol regulatory
160 element binding transcription factor 1 *SREBF1*; peroxisome proliferator activated receptor
161 gamma, *PPARG*), MTOR pathway components (*MTOR*; eukaryotic translation initiation factor
162 4E binding protein 1, *EIF4EBP1*; ribosomal protein S6 kinase B1, *RPS6KB1*), activation of
163 transcription and translation (mitogen-activated protein kinase 1, *MAPK1*), insulin signaling

164 (insulin receptor substrate 1, *IRS1*; *AKT* serine/threonine kinase 1 and 2, *AKT1*, *AKT2*), and
165 mammary cell turnover (marker of proliferation Ki-67, *MKI67*; BCL2 like 1, *BCL2L1*; BCL2
166 associated X, apoptosis regulator, *BAX*). The geometric mean of glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate
167 dehydrogenase (*GADPH*), ubiquitously expressed prefoldin like chaperone (*UXT*), and
168 ribosomal protein S9 (*RPS9*) was used to normalize mRNA abundance. Each sample and a 6-
169 point relative standard curve plus the non-template control were run in triplicate. All qPCR
170 reactions were performed in an ABI Prism 7900 HT SDS instrument (Applied Biosystems) at 95
171 °C for 5 min, followed by 40 cycles at 95 °C for 1 s, and 60 °C for 30 s. The presence of a single
172 PCR product was verified by the dissociation protocol using incremental temperatures to 95 °C
173 for 15 s, 65 °C for 15 s, and 95 °C for 15 s. Data were analyzed using the standard curve with the
174 7900 HT Sequence Detection Systems Software (version 2.4, Applied Biosystems). Methods for
175 primer design and validation as well as primer sequences were as reported as previously (Bionaz
176 and Loor, 2011).

177 ***MicroRNA Extraction and Quantitative Real Time PCR***

178 The miRNA were extracted from cells according to the manufacturer's protocol (mir-Vana
179 miRNA Isolation Kit, AM1561; Applied Biosystems). Ribonucleic acid (10 µg) was
180 polyadenylated using Poly(A) polymerase according to the manufacturer's instructions (NCode
181 miRNA, First Strand cDNA Module, no. 45-6612; Invitrogen). Complementary DNA was made
182 as follows: 10 µg of polyadenylated RNA was reverse-transcribed using Superscript II reverse
183 transcriptase (Invitrogen) with 2.5 µg of random hexamers and 500 ng of oligo (dT) adapter
184 primer (Invitrogen), according to the manufacturer's instructions.

185 The reactions were performed in triplicate as follows: 5 µL of cDNA were mixed with 5 pmol
186 of both the forward (F) and reverse (R) primers in a final volume of 12.5 µL and mixed with 12.5

187 μ L of 2 \times Power SYBR Green PCR Master Mix (No. 4367659; Applied Biosystems). All
188 reactions were run using 2 amplification protocols: 20 s at 94 °C, 30 s at 59 °C, and 20 s at 72 °C
189 for 40 cycles. The same conditions were performed on an equal amount of RNase-free water as a
190 negative control. Primer sequences are reported in Suppl. Table 1.

191 Real-time quantitative PCR with SYBR Green I (Power SYBR Green, PCR Master Mix, No.
192 4367659; Applied Biosystems) was performed in an ABI Prism 7900 HT SDS instrument
193 (Applied Biosystems), and the data were calculated with 7900 HT Sequence Detection Systems
194 software (version 2.2.1; Applied Biosystems). The geometric mean of 5S (catalog no. AM30302;
195 Applied Biosystems) and U6 was used to normalize the expression of target miRNA.

196 ***Western Blotting***

197 Total protein from each of the 3 replicates per treatment was extracted using tissue protein
198 extraction reagent (catalog no. 78510; Thermo Scientific), which included inhibitor Cocktail
199 (100x, catalog no. 78442; Thermo Scientific). The concentrations of total protein were
200 determined with the BCA assay kit (catalog no. 23227; Thermo Scientific). Protein samples were
201 boiled at 100 °C for 10 min; 80 μ g of total protein per lane was resolved by SDS-PAGE and then
202 transferred to PVDF membrane (catalog no. 1620261; Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA) by using the
203 semi-dry transfer assembly (Bio-Rad). Membranes were blocked in Tris-buffered saline (TBST;
204 50 mM Tris, pH 7.6, 150 mM NaCl, and 0.1% Tween 20) which contains 5% (w/v) nonfat milk
205 for 2 h at room temperature with gentle agitation. The membranes were then incubated in TBST
206 with 5% nonfat milk containing antibodies to MTOR, p-MTOR, RPS6KB1, p-RPS6KB1,
207 EIF4EBP1, p-EIF4EBP1, EIF2A, p-EIF2A, EEF2, p-EEF2, AKT and p-AKT (catalog no.
208 2972A, 2971S, 9202S, 9234S, 9452S, 9459S, 5324P, 3398S, 2332S, 2331S, 9272S, and 9272S,
209 respectively; Cell Signaling Technology) with gentle agitation at 4 °C overnight. After

210 incubating with primary antibody, the membranes were washed and incubated with HRP-
211 conjugated secondary antibodies (catalog no. ab6721; Abcam) in TBST for 1 h at room
212 temperature. The membranes were washed and then incubated with ECL reagent (catalog no.
213 170-5060; Bio-Rad). GAPDH (catalog no. ab22555; Abcam) and tubulin (catalog no. 2144S;
214 Cell Signaling Technology) were the internal controls. The images were captured using
215 ChemiDOC MP (Bio-Rad). The intensities of the bands were measured with Image-Pro Plus 6.0
216 software (Media Cybernetics, Inc., Rockville, MD).

217 *Statistical analyses and Calculations*

218 Western blot data with non-normal distribution and all mRNA abundance data were log₂
219 transformed to obtain a normal distribution before statistical analysis. Statistical analysis was
220 performed using the MIXED model in SAS (version 9.3, SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC). The
221 qPCR data were normalized using the geometric mean of the 3 internal control genes (*GADPH*,
222 *UXT*, and *RPS9*) for mRNA, and both 5S and U6 for miRNA prior to log₂ transformation. The
223 statistical model included the main effects of AA supplementation (Con, Met, and Arg),
224 temperature (TN vs. HS), and their interaction as fixed effects. The Kenward-Roger statement
225 was used for computing the denominator degrees of freedom. Treatment means were compared
226 using the PDIFF statement in SAS after correction using Tukey's. Significance was declared at a
227 PDIFF Tukey-adjusted $P < 0.05$.

228 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

229 Core body temperatures above 41 °C have been reported in heat-stressed dairy cows and
230 goats (Baumgard and Rhoads, 2013; Salama et al., 2014). Furthermore, Collier et al. (2006), Mu
231 et al. (2014), and Han et al. (2015) also stressed bovine mammary cells at 42 °C. Thus, our
232 choice of HS temperature was in accordance to previous work of similar nature. The fact that

233 mRNA abundance of the heat shock protein gene (discussed below) in cells undergoing HS
234 indicated that thermotolerance was not lost by 6 h of treatment at 42°C. Overall, previous and
235 present data underscore the suitability of the chosen temperature and incubation time to address
236 the specific hypothesis and objectives of the study.

237 *Heat Stress and Amino Acid Responses on mRNA and Protein Abundance*

238 A dramatic upregulation ($P < 0.001$) of *HSPA1A* (70 kDa HSP) abundance was observed
239 with HS (Table 2), confirming data from a previous study with bovine mammary epithelial cells
240 incubated at 42 °C for 30 min (Han et al., 2015). In the study of Han et al. (2015), protein
241 abundance of *HSPA1A* also increased with HS. The protein encoded by this gene plays a
242 heightened role in cell cryoprotection and is frequently used as a biomarker of cellular stress
243 (Sonna et al., 2002). Levels of heat shock proteins increase dramatically, but transiently, in cells
244 exposed to an insult as a mechanism to bind to unfolded or misfolded proteins and help restore
245 their native conformation (Feder and Hofmann, 1999).

246 The *HSPA1A* was also upregulated ($P < 0.001$) by both Met and Arg, especially under
247 HS conditions (Table 2). The upregulation of *HSPA1A* when Met and Arg were supplemented
248 suggests that under HS conditions an increase in the supply of Met and Arg (and probably other
249 AA) to mammary cells could be channeled for synthesis of extra proteins that serve a protective
250 role. Such role has been reported for Met as it can increase *HSPA1A* expression during heat
251 stress, oxidative stress, and other stress states in cells or tissues (Han et al., 2015).

252 With regard to AA transporters, we detected an upregulation ($P < 0.001$) of the
253 abundance of *SLC1A5* (MTOR related) and *SLC7A1* (MTOR unrelated) with HS (Table 2).
254 Assuming that the synthesis rate of cytoprotective proteins increases during HS, an increase in
255 the use of AA to synthesize more HSP appears logical. This condition would result in the

256 upregulation of AA transporters to meet the increased requirements of producing cytoprotective
257 proteins. Pirkkala et al. (2001) revealed that HS increases production of proteins necessary for
258 restoring normal cellular function and directing cellular remodeling (structural proteins, cell-
259 cycle control proteins, and proteins involved in pro- and anti-apoptotic pathways).

260 Heat stress did not affect ($P > 0.05$) the abundance of *IRS1* or *AKT1*, but upregulated ($P <$
261 0.05) *AKT2* (Table 2). In contrast, Met supplementation upregulated ($P < 0.05$) *IRS1* and *AKT2*
262 abundance, while Arg only upregulated ($P < 0.05$) abundance of *AKT1*. Bionaz and Loor (2011)
263 revealed that one of the mechanisms in the mammary gland to enhance insulin (or IGF-1)
264 sensitivity as lactation progresses is the upregulation of the IRS1-PDK-AKT signaling pathway.
265 In the present study, the fact that Met supplementation had an effect on *IRS1* and *AKT2* during
266 HS suggests that it can potentially enhance insulin sensitivity under stress conditions.

267 Abundance of *STAT5B* ($P < 0.001$), a component of the JAK-STAT signaling pathway, was
268 upregulated with HS. Additionally, *JAK2* abundance was upregulated ($P < 0.001$) with Met and
269 Arg supplementation, but no effect was observed on *STAT5B* (Table 2). A role for STAT5 in
270 controlling milk protein gene expression through the Jak2-Stat5 signaling pathway has been
271 reported (Bionaz and Loor, 2011). It is possible that these changes in the abundance of STAT5
272 and JAK are related to the increase in synthesis of cytoprotective proteins during HS.

273 Although HS had no effect on *MAPK1* abundance, the supplementation with Met or Arg
274 increased its abundance (Table 2). Evidence indicates that MAPK1 could induce protein
275 synthesis in bovine mammary cells through the phosphorylation of MTOR and STAT5 (Lu et al.,
276 2013). Taking into account that increasing the supplementation of Lys led to greater protein
277 content of MAPK1 in bovine mammary cells (Lu et al., 2013) the present data suggest that Met
278 and Arg could elicit a similar effect.

279 There was temperature and AA interaction ($P < 0.05$) effect on *HSP70A1A*, *MTOR*, *EIF4BP1*,
280 *IRS1*, *AKT1*, and *JAK2* abundance (Table 2). This interaction resulted from the fact that Met or
281 Arg supplementation had more marked effect during HS than TN conditions.

282 Heat stress downregulated ($P < 0.01$) the abundance of *PPARG* without affecting
283 *SREBF1* (Table 2). Furthermore, HS downregulated ($P < 0.01$) *ACACA* and *FASN*. Although the
284 current study is in vitro, the obtained results agree with the fact that HS consistently decreases
285 the concentration of de novo-synthesized FA in milk of dairy cows (Hammami et al., 2015).

286 Supplementation of Met upregulated ($P < 0.01$) the abundance of both *PPARG* and
287 *SREBF1*, whereas Arg upregulated only *SREBF1*. Additionally, Arg and Met supplementation
288 did not affect *ACACA*, but enhanced ($P < 0.001$) the abundance of *FASN*. A significant
289 interaction ($P < 0.05$) between temperature and AA supplementation was detected for *PPARG*
290 and *FASN* abundance (Table 2). These data suggest the existence of a mechanism whereby AA
291 supplementation (especially Met) can directly or indirectly impact milk fat synthesis. It is known
292 that *SREBF1* plays important roles in milk fat depression induced by greater availability of
293 *trans10*, *cis12*-CLA to mammary cells (Ma and Corl, 2012). Additionally, in vitro data
294 demonstrated that various lipogenic genes (*ACACA*, *FASN* and *SCD*) are direct targets of
295 *PPARG* in goat mammary cells (Shi et al., 2013). Thus, the negative effect of HS on *PPARG*
296 expression might explain at least in part the decrease in fat synthesis capacity of mammary cells
297 in dairy animals exposed to hyperthermia.

298 The expression of *MKI67*, *BCL2L1*, and *BAX* was used to evaluate proliferation, anti-
299 apoptotic and pro-apoptotic responses in mammary epithelial cells, respectively. Exposure to HS
300 did not seem to affect ($P > 0.05$) proliferation, but downregulated ($P < 0.001$) anti-apoptotic and
301 upregulated pro-apoptotic signals (Table 2). A previous study reported that incubation of bovine

302 mammary cells at 42 °C for 30 min decreased proliferation and increased apoptosis (Han et al.,
303 2015). Because HS reduces antioxidant capacity and increases free radicals at the systemic and
304 cellular levels (Liu et al., 2010), such a mechanism could have accounted for the observed
305 responses in *BCL2L1* and *BAX*. Additionally, HS induces a number of abnormalities in cell
306 function, including the inhibition of protein synthesis, changes in protein folding and function,
307 and changes in metabolism and membrane fluidity, all of which reduce proliferation and increase
308 apoptosis in cultured bovine mammary cells (Collier et al. 2006).

309 The supplementation with Arg and Met upregulated ($P < 0.01$) the abundance of *MKI67*
310 (mammary proliferation) and *BCL2L1* (antiapoptotic) (Table 2). Similarly, Han et al. (2015)
311 reported that, by reducing the oxidative stress, increasing supply of Met markedly decreased the
312 mortality of cultured bovine mammary cells that suffered hyperthermia. In fact, increased Met
313 supply in heat-stressed mammary cells decreased malondialdehyde and nitric oxide
314 concentrations along with nitric oxide synthase (all indicators of oxidative stress) (Han et al.,
315 2015). Additionally, Met had a positive effect on superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione
316 peroxidase enzymatic activities (antioxidant enzymes). Thus, Met supply seems to be effective at
317 providing some protection against cellular damage in large part through its antioxidant action
318 (Osorio et al., 2014).

319 One of the primary uses of Arg by the mammary gland is for conversion to ornithine and
320 nitric oxide (O'Quinn et al., 2002). The metabolic end-products of the conversion of Arg to
321 ornithine are putrescine, spermidine, and spermine (Wu et al., 2009). Putrescine has positive
322 effects on cell proliferation (Chen et al., 2015), which might explain the positive effect of Arg on
323 *MKI67* expression (Table 2). In fact, inhibition of the Arg – ornithine pathway (via inhibition of
324 arginase) reduced mammary cell proliferation (Wang et al., 2017). The significant temperature

325 and AA interaction detected for *BCL2L1* and *BAX* abundance (Table 2) was due to the fact that
326 AA supplementation upregulated mRNA abundance to a greater extent under HS than TN
327 conditions.

328 Exposure to HS did not alter ($P > 0.05$) mRNA abundance of *AKT1*, but upregulated
329 *AKT2* ($P < 0.001$) (Table 2). However, total and phosphorylated AKT protein abundances were
330 reduced ($P < 0.001$) by HS (Table 3). Exposure to HS also decreased ($P < 0.001$) total protein
331 abundance of MTOR (Table 3) without affecting its mRNA abundance (Table 2) or
332 phosphorylation (Table 3). Despite the upregulation in mRNA abundance of EIF4EBP1 with HS
333 (0.46 vs. -0.14; $P < 0.001$), its total protein abundance was lower (1.19 vs. 1.57; $P < 0.001$).
334 Hence, the inhibitory effect of HS on mammary protein synthesis typically observed in vivo
335 could be explained by the hypophosphorylation of EIF4EBP1 detected in the current study (1.68
336 vs. 2.73; $P < 0.001$). Furthermore, the fact that HS did not change MTOR phosphorylation
337 (Table 3) suggests that the effect on EIF4EBP1 was independent of MTOR. The lower ratio of
338 phosphorylated to total EIF4BP1 protein in control cells during HS (Figure 1) could be related to
339 the lower milk protein content usually observed in dairy animals under HS conditions.

340 Temperature had no effect ($P > 0.05$) on the phosphorylation of RPS6KB1 or RPS6
341 (Table 3). With regards to other important components of the protein synthesis network, namely
342 the integrated stress network, HS compared with TN tended to increase ($P = 0.10$) the
343 phosphorylation of EIF2A. Greater phosphorylation of EIF2A is associated with lower milk
344 protein synthesis (Baird and Wek, 2012). With regard to translation elongation, exposure to HS
345 decreased ($P < 0.05$) total and phosphorylated protein abundance of EEF2, but the
346 phosphorylation ratio was not affected by HS (6.25 vs. 5.13 for TN and HS, respectively; SEM =
347 1.16, $P = 0.382$). Along with the response observed for EIF4EBP1 (Tables 2 and 3), the decrease

348 in EEF2 protein abundance with HS (Table 3) seems to be part of the mechanism responsible for
349 the lower milk protein content usually observed in animals exposed to high ambient
350 temperatures.

351 Supplementation with Met and Arg increased ($P < 0.001$) the abundance of total AKT,
352 while phosphorylated AKT increased ($P < 0.01$) only with Arg (Table 3). The kinase AKT plays
353 an important role in the regulation of MTOR activity by sensing signals related to cell
354 differentiation, proliferation, and apoptosis (Reddi et al., 2016). Despite the change in AKT
355 abundance, protein abundance of MTOR or phosphorylated MTOR did not differ in response to
356 Met or Arg supplementation (Table 3). This result was unexpected because (at least in non-
357 ruminants) the phosphorylation status of AKT and MTOR is often consistent. However, our
358 results agree with Dong et al. (2018) who detected that Met supplementation to achieve a
359 Lys:Met of 2.5 (from 2:9:1 in the control) in MAC-T cells decreased MTOR but increased AKT
360 phosphorylation. Thus, at least in vitro, a mismatch between AKT and MTOR phosphorylation
361 in response to Arg supplementation could also occur. The exact reason for this type of response
362 is unclear.

363 ***Heat Stress and Amino Acid Responses on microRNA Abundance***

364 Heat stress upregulated ($P < 0.05$) the abundance of miR-34a, miR-92a, miR-99 and
365 miR-184 by 42, 62, 113, and 19%, respectively (Table 4). Upregulation of miR-34a induced
366 apoptosis in Hep2 cells (Wang et al., 2016b) and mammary cells (Jena, 2017), and inhibited cell
367 proliferation (Wang et al., 2016b). Hermeking (2010) showed that a number of genes targeted by
368 miR-34a are suppressed, resulting in growth arrest and greater levels of apoptosis (Smith et al.
369 (2015) reported that miR-92 inhibition exerts an oncogenic role within mammary cells by down-
370 regulating the expression of specific anti-proliferative and/or pro-apoptotic genes. Furthermore,

371 Hu et al. (2014) showed that overexpression of miR-99a reduces breast cancer cell viability by
372 inducing accumulation of cells at the sub-G1 phase leading to apoptosis.

373 The activation of miR-184 also inhibits proliferation and self-renewal of triple negative
374 breast cancer cell lines in vitro, and delayed primary tumor formation and reduced metastatic
375 burden in vivo (Phua et al., 2015). Together, these findings suggest that overexpression of miR-
376 34a, miR-92a, miR-99, and miR-184 would lead to cell growth arrest, which agrees with the fact
377 that the pro-apoptotic gene BAX was upregulated with HS in the current study (Table 2).

378 Abundance of miR-141 and miR-200a was upregulated ($P < 0.01$) by HS (Table 4). At
379 least in non-ruminants, miR-200a and miR-141 are thought to interact with the same target sites
380 (Nagaoka et al., 2013) and both are overexpressed in tissues with high levels of oxidative stress
381 (Magenta et al., 2017). Specifically, miR-200a regulates the Keap1/Nrf2 pathway in mammary
382 epithelium, which is related to the oxidative stress (Eades et al., 2011). Thus, when miR-200a is
383 upregulated cellular oxidative stress is increased. Although we did not measure oxidative stress
384 in the present study, HS has been shown to increase cell oxidative stress and the accumulation of
385 free radicals and peroxides (Liu et al., 2010). Thus, we speculate that the overexpression of miR-
386 200a during HS was related to cellular oxidative stress.

387 The abundance of miR-27ab and miR-221 during HS was upregulated ($P < 0.001$) by 32
388 and 67%, respectively (Table 4). Tang et al. (2017) reported that the overexpression of miR-27a
389 in bovine mammary cells significantly suppresses lipid droplet formation, decreases cellular
390 triacylglycerol levels, and inhibits mRNA abundance of *PPARG*. In addition, Chu et al. (2018)
391 reported that inhibition of miR-221 increased lipid content in mammary epithelial cells through
392 elevation of the lipid synthesis enzyme *FASN*, while overexpression of miR-221 decreased
393 mammary epithelial cell lipid content. In the current study, HS downregulated abundance of

394 *FASN* and *PPARG* (Table 2), which could have been mediated by the overexpression of miR-221
395 and miR-27ab, respectively.

396 Both Met and Arg supplementation downregulated ($P < 0.05$) abundance of miR-23a.
397 This miRNA has been shown to control abundance of genes related to milk fat synthesis (Zhang
398 et al., 2014). Thus, we speculate that the positive effect of Met and Arg on the abundance of
399 *PPARG*, *SREBF1*, and *FASN* (Table 2) could have been mediated by the change in abundance of
400 miR-23a. Additionally, Met supplementation downregulated ($P < 0.05$) abundance of miR-26a.
401 This miRNA represses cyclin D2 and cyclin E2, which play critical roles in the transition
402 through the G1-S checkpoint, hence, it plays a role in cellular apoptosis (Kota et al., 2009). Thus,
403 at least at the molecular level, the data suggest a positive effect of Met on reducing mammary
404 cellular apoptosis.

405 Although Arg upregulated abundance of *SREBF1* and *FASN* (Table 2), it also
406 upregulated miR-221 (Table 4), which has a negative effect on fat synthesis (Chu et al., 2018). It
407 is possible that the effect of Arg on inhibition of miR-23a overcomes the upregulation of miR-
408 221, with the net result of enhancing milk fat synthesis. Furthermore, Met supplementation
409 upregulated miR-141 during HS but not TN conditions resulting in a significant interaction
410 between temperature and AA (Table 4). Because miR-141 is a member of miR-200 family that
411 responds to increased levels of oxidative stress, its upregulation with Met during HS is unclear.
412 In fact, Met protects against hyperthermia-induced oxidative stress in cultured bovine mammary
413 epithelial cells (Han et al., 2015). Further research will help clarify the relationship between Met
414 and miRNA in the mammary gland.

415 **CONCLUSIONS**

416 Heat stress causes changes at the molecular level in mammary cells. These changes are related
417 to the synthesis of milk components and mammary cell turnover. The inhibitory effect of heat
418 stress on milk protein synthesis could be due to the hypophosphorylation of EIF4EBP1, and it
419 seems independent of the MTOR pathway. Heat stress negatively affects milk fat synthesis by
420 downregulating de novo fatty acid synthesis genes through decreasing *PPARG* gene expression,
421 but not *SREBF1*. Methionine and arginine supplementation has a positive effect on milk
422 synthesis by upregulating *FASN* and activating both *PPARG* and *SREBF1*. Additionally, heat
423 stress did not affect mammary proliferation, but upregulated pro-apoptotic signals. On the other
424 hand, Met and Arg supplementation upregulated mammary cell proliferation, but did not affect
425 apoptosis. Effects of heat stress and AA were related to changes in the expression of various
426 miRNA controlling apoptosis, proliferation, oxidative stress and fat synthesis. Additionally,
427 findings raise the possibility that supplemental amino acids (especially methionine) during heat
428 stress might have a positive effect on mammary metabolism.

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601 **Table 1.** Amino acid (AA) composition of the experimental lactogenic media¹ used for cultured
 602 (6 h) of the bovine mammary epithelial cell line MAC-T.

AA	Treatments		
	Control	Met	Arg
Composition, µg/mL			
Lys	175	175	175
Met	60	70	60
Thr	97	97	97
Phe	92	92	92
His	74	74	74
Val	142	142	142
Ile	121	121	121
Leu	206	206	206
Arg	84	84	168
Trp	16	16	16
Ratio			
Lys:Met	2.9:1.0	2.5:1.0	2.9:1.0
Lys:Arg	2.1:1.0	2.1:1.0	1.0:1.0

603 ¹Custom HG-DMEM devoid of all essential AA was used

604 **Table 2.** Effects of incubating mammary cells in thermal-neutral (37 °C) or hyper thermal (heat
605 stress, 42 °C) conditions (6 h) with an ideal ratio of Lysine to Methionine (Lys:Met 2.9:1; Con)
606 or treatments containing Lys:Met at 2.5:1 (Met) or Lys:Arg 1.0:1.0 (Arg) on mRNA abundance
607 (log-scale) of genes associated with heat stress, MTOR pathway, lipogenesis, and cell turnover.

Gene	Thermal-neutral			Heat stress			SEM ¹	P value ²		
	Con	Met	Arg	Con	Met	Arg		Temp	AA	T×AA
<i>HSP70A1A</i>	0.12 ^d	0.30 ^c	0.27 ^c	1.16 ^b	18.21 ^a	6.82 ^a	8.03	0.001	0.001	0.001
<i>MTOR</i>	0.78 ^b	0.99 ^a	0.81 ^{ab}	0.63 ^b	1.44 ^a	0.88 ^{ab}	0.30	0.350	0.013	0.018
<i>EIF4EBP1</i>	0.85 ^b	0.66 ^c	1.31 ^a	1.62 ^a	0.65 ^b	2.47 ^a	0.87	0.001	0.008	0.031
<i>RPS6KB1</i>	1.15 ^y	1.82 ^x	1.62 ^{xy}	1.37 ^y	3.36 ^x	2.23 ^{xy}	1.23	0.012	0.075	0.446
<i>IRS1</i>	0.90	0.89	0.90	0.87 ^b	0.98 ^a	0.88 ^b	0.02	0.501	0.052	0.017
<i>AKT1</i>	1.44 ^c	2.68 ^b	7.53 ^a	0.54 ^b	1.51 ^b	12.9 ^a	8.25	0.114	0.001	0.014
<i>AKT2</i>	0.22 ^y	0.42 ^x	0.35 ^{xy}	0.69 ^y	3.12 ^x	1.89 ^{xy}	1.40	0.001	0.012	0.145
<i>SLC1A5</i>	0.57	0.73	1.26	2.96	3.72	8.36	4.50	0.001	0.124	0.773
<i>SLC7A1</i>	0.97 ^y	1.12 ^{xy}	1.50 ^x	1.25	1.58	2.35	0.71	0.001	0.101	0.727
<i>JAK2</i>	0.62 ^b	1.60 ^a	2.12 ^a	0.39 ^b	2.52 ^a	4.67 ^a	2.27	0.098	0.001	0.005
<i>JAK2</i>	0.62 ^c	1.60 ^b	2.12 ^b	0.39 ^c	2.52 ^{ab}	4.67 ^a	2.27	0.098	0.001	0.005
<i>STAT5B</i>	0.81	0.76	0.97	1.68	1.17	1.74	0.42	0.001	0.278	0.261
<i>MAPK1</i>	0.83 ^y	1.53 ^x	1.61 ^x	0.64 ^y	1.65 ^x	1.80 ^x	0.80	0.864	0.010	0.498
<i>PPARG</i>	0.90 ^b	1.30 ^a	1.28 ^a	0.94 ^{ab}	1.13 ^a	0.84 ^b	0.09	0.008	0.002	0.019
<i>SREBF1</i>	0.71 ^y	1.30 ^x	1.47 ^x	0.46 ^y	1.50 ^x	1.94 ^x	1.03	0.968	0.008	0.176
<i>ACACA</i>	1.21	1.30	1.31	0.70	0.67	0.62	1.75	0.001	0.833	0.336
<i>FASN</i>	1.05 ^b	2.19 ^a	1.86 ^a	0.18 ^b	0.96 ^a	0.63 ^a	0.42	0.001	0.001	0.042
<i>MKI67</i>	1.23 ^z	3.32 ^y	8.70 ^x	0.83 ^y	3.01 ^y	18.4 ^x	14.1	0.719	0.001	0.150
<i>BCL2L1</i>	0.61 ^b	3.63 ^a	3.62 ^a	0.01 ^b	5.50 ^a	4.48 ^a	3.52	0.001	0.001	0.001
<i>BAX</i>	0.38 ^c	0.36 ^c	0.36 ^c	0.46 ^b	0.49 ^a	0.46 ^b	0.01	0.001	0.287	0.034

608 ^{a,-d} Indicate differences ($P < 0.05$) between means across temperature and AA treatments when T×AA is
609 significant

610 ^{x,-z} Indicate differences ($P < 0.05$) between means within each temperature treatment when T×AA is not
611 significant

612 ¹ Largest SEM for T×AA

613 ² Temp = temperature; AA = amino acid

614

615 **Table 3.** Effects of incubating mammary cells in thermal-neutral (37 °C) or hyper thermal (heat
616 stress, 42 °C) conditions (6 h) with an ideal ratio of Lysine to Methionine (Lys:Met 2.9:1; Con)
617 or treatments containing Lys:Met at 2.5:1 (Met) or Lys:Arg 1.0:1.0 (Arg) on total and
618 phosphorylated protein abundance (arbitrary units) of components of the insulin and MTOR
619 signaling pathways.

Protein	Thermal-neutral			Heat stress			SEM	<i>P</i> values ²		
	Con	Met	Arg	Con	Met	Arg		Temp	AA	T×A
Total MTOR	0.67 ^b	0.87 ^a	0.73 ^{ab}	0.53 ^a	0.36 ^b	0.44 ^{ab}	0.05	0.001	0.841	0.005
p-MTOR	0.22	0.20	0.51	0.22	0.24	0.08	0.23	0.105	0.929	0.032
Total EIF4EBP1	0.82 ^b	0.95 ^b	2.95 ^a	0.87 ^b	0.71 ^b	1.99 ^a	0.10	0.001	0.001	0.001
p-EIF4EBP1	4.31 ^a	2.98 ^b	0.91 ^c	2.07 ^a	2.47 ^a	0.50 ^b	0.17	0.001	0.001	0.001
Total RPS6KB1	0.88 ^y	2.63 ^x	0.61 ^y	1.00 ^y	2.63 ^x	0.74 ^y	0.12	0.405	0.001	0.823
p-RPS6KB1	0.27 ^b	0.45 ^a	0.40 ^a	0.44	0.05	0.32	0.27	0.858	0.237	0.046
Total RPS6	13.5	12.6	8.96	6.07	10.8	13.5	9.06	0.623	0.951	0.282
p-RPS6	30.9	24.0	65.0	43.1	19.9	72.6	27.0	0.580	0.213	0.765
Total EEF2	1.18 ^c	2.72 ^b	3.47 ^a	1.91 ^a	0.79 ^b	1.54 ^a	0.23	0.001	0.001	0.001
p-EEF2	12.5 ^b	3.90 ^c	22.2 ^a	8.32	4.81	5.20	1.56	0.001	0.001	0.001
Total AKT	4.13 ^c	11.8 ^a	7.38 ^b	2.18	1.25	3.05	0.88	0.001	0.002	0.001
p-AKT	1.27 ^y	1.38 ^y	2.27 ^x	0.60 ^y	0.75 ^y	1.48 ^x	0.17	0.001	0.001	0.884
Total EIF2A	7.17 ^y	21.9 ^x	1.19 ^y	7.69 ^y	24.9 ^x	-2.74 ^y	8.00	0.961	0.005	0.538
p-EIF2A	0.61	0.61	1.69	1.88	0.83	1.56	0.84	0.102	0.476	0.104

620 ^{a,-d} Indicate differences ($P < 0.05$) between means across temperature and AA treatments when T×AA is
621 significant

622 ^{x,y} Indicate differences ($P < 0.05$) between means within each temperature treatment when T×AA is not
623 significant

624

625 ¹ Largest SEM for T×AA

626 ² Temp = temperature; AA = amino acid

627 **Table 4.** Effects of incubating mammary cells in thermal neutral (37 °C) or hyper thermal (heat
628 stress, 42 °C) conditions with an ideal AA ratio (Lys:Met 2.9:1; Con) or treatments containing
629 Lys:Met at 2.5:1 (Met) or Lys:Arg 1.0:1.0 (Arg) on abundance (log-scale) of microRNA
630 (miRNA).

miRNA	Thermal-neutral			Heat stress			SEM ¹	<i>P</i> value ²		
	Con	Met	Arg	Con	Met	Arg		Temp	AA	T×AA
<i>miR-23a</i>	1.38 ^x	0.69 ^y	0.84 ^{xy}	1.85 ^x	0.51 ^y	0.69 ^{xy}	0.63	0.688	0.017	0.314
<i>miR-26a</i>	1.47 ^x	0.63 ^y	1.09 ^{xy}	2.32 ^x	0.61 ^y	1.75 ^{xy}	0.97	0.111	0.022	0.434
<i>miR-27ab</i>	0.77	0.81	0.93	1.04	1.23	1.07	0.22	0.001	0.669	0.318
<i>miR-34a</i>	1.24	0.87	0.99	2.04	1.38	0.96	0.59	0.043	0.279	0.275
<i>miR-92a</i>	1.41	0.86	1.22	2.92	1.26	1.46	1.08	0.024	0.209	0.488
<i>miR-99</i>	1.26	0.67	1.66	2.52	0.88	4.29	3.06	0.007	0.119	0.500
<i>miR-103</i>	0.70	0.62	0.69	0.81	0.65	0.60	0.28	0.905	0.830	0.717
<i>miR-141</i>	1.21	1.48	0.60	1.57 ^b	6.60 ^a	0.59 ^b	3.60	0.007	0.024	0.011
<i>miR-141</i>	1.21 ^b	1.48 ^b	0.60 ^c	1.57 ^b	6.60 ^a	0.59 ^{bc}	3.60	0.007	0.024	0.011
<i>miR-184</i>	0.74	0.74	0.91	0.92	0.86	1.07	0.25	0.032	0.572	0.943
<i>miR-200a</i>	1.00	0.67	0.76	1.35	1.04	0.98	0.32	0.004	0.260	0.776
<i>miR-221</i>	0.60	0.64	0.75	1.10	1.05	1.16	0.06	0.001	0.024	0.290

631 ^{a,c} Indicate differences (*P* < 0.05) between means across temperature and AA treatments when T×AA is
632 significant

633 ^{x,y} Indicate differences (*P* < 0.05) between means within each temperature treatment when T×AA is not
634 significant

635 ¹ Largest SEM for T×AA

636 ² Temp = temperature; AA = amino acid

Figure 1

FIGURE LEGEND

Figure 1. Effects of incubating mammary cells in thermal neutral (TN, 37 °C) or hyper thermal (HS, 42 °C) conditions with the ideal amino acid ratio (Lys:Met 2.9:1; Control) or treatments containing Lys:Met at 2.5:1 (Met) or Lys:Arg 1.0:1.0 (Arg) on the ratio of phosphorylated protein to total protein (arbitrary units) of components of the insulin and MTOR pathways.

^{ab}Means differ ($P < 0.05$; temperature \times amino acid effect). EIF2A, p-EIF2A/total EIF2A; MTOR, p-MTOR/total MTOR; p-RPS6/total RPS6; p-EEF2/total EEF2; p-AKT/total AKT; p-RPS6KB1/total RPS6KB1.